

Estimation of Subsistence Gillnet Effort and Chinook Salmon Harvest in Non-Salmon Spawning Tributaries of the Lower Kuskokwim River

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ABSTRACT

Since 2010, Chinook Salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*) returns to the Kuskokwim River have been below average, prompting fishing restrictions in the mainstem of the Kuskokwim River and salmon spawning tributaries. Coinciding with these closures, non-salmon spawning tributaries of the Kuskokwim River have remained generally unrestricted to subsistence fishing throughout the drainage. In response to restrictions in the mainstem Kuskokwim River and the absence of restrictions in the non-salmon tributaries, some subsistence users have used gillnets to harvest milling Chinook Salmon in non-salmon spawning tributaries, even though opportunities to fish in non-salmon spawning tributaries are intended for the harvest of fish other than salmon. This has led to concern by some subsistence users, who characterize the harvest as a misuse of non-salmon spawning tributary fishing opportunities to target Chinook Salmon. Given these issues, and the general lack of harvest and effort information in non-salmon spawning tributaries, the United States Fish and Wildlife Service in collaboration with a community based monitoring program conducted by the Bering Sea Fishermen's Association, collected data via aerial and creel surveys to inform subsistence effort and harvest estimates in several prominent non-salmon spawning tributaries within the Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge: Eenayarak, Tagayarak, Kinak, Kialik, Johnson, and Gweek rivers. From May 28 to July 8, 2018, an estimated total of 785 nets (95% CI: 641 – 931), comprised of 539 set gillnets (95% CI: 426 – 665) and 246 drift gillnets (95% CI: 167 – 342), were fished during all daylight flood tides in these non-salmon spawning tributaries. In general, set nets were most commonly used; however, drift nets were used more frequently than set nets during the latter half of June. The tributary locations with the most netting effort were the Gweek and Johnson rivers (~70% of observed gillnets), followed by the Kinak and Tagararak rivers (~20% of observed gillnets), and the Eenayarak and Kialik rivers (~10% of observed gillnets). While the project was able to collect some harvest information from non-salmon spawning tributaries during six subsistence salmon gillnet fishing mainstem opportunities ($n = 18$ interviews), the sample size was too limited to be representative, so construction of unbiased harvest estimates was not possible.

INTRODUCTION

Since 2010, Chinook Salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*) returns to the Kuskokwim River have been below average, prompting fishing restrictions in the mainstem and salmon spawning tributaries of the Kuskokwim River (Poetter and Tiernan 2017, Liller et al. 2018). These restrictions have affected traditional salmon fishing practices and opportunities, resulting in significant hardships for subsistence users who rely on Chinook Salmon. Harvest of fish in non-salmon spawning tributaries of the Kuskokwim River have generally remained unrestricted (no gillnet restrictions above 100 yards of the confluence with mainstem) throughout the drainage while the mainstem and salmon spawning tributaries have been heavily restricted (limited time window opportunities with gillnet restrictions). These non-salmon spawning tributary locations are traditionally used to harvest non-salmon species. Unrestricted fishing opportunities are available in tributaries found in the lower Kuskokwim River, within the boundaries of the Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge (YKNWR), including the Eenayarak, Tagayarak, Kinak, Kialik, Johnson, and Gweek rivers (**Figure 1**).

In response to restrictions in the mainstem Kuskokwim River and the absence of restrictions in the non-salmon tributaries, some subsistence harvest of milling Chinook Salmon in non-salmon spawning tributaries has occurred, even though fishing in non-salmon spawning tributaries was intended as opportunities for the traditional harvest of fish other than salmon (i.e. Sheefish (*Stenodus nelma*), whitefish spp., Northern Pike (*Esox Lucius*), etc.). While post-season estimates indicated total Chinook Salmon abundance during the 2015 – 2017 seasons were sufficient to exceed the lower bound of the escapement goal range and allow for some subsistence harvest (Liller et al. 2018), concerns were voiced by some subsistence users about this harvest of Chinook Salmon and characterized it as a misuse of non-salmon spawning tributary fishing opportunities.

Given these concerns, the Federal in-season manager felt it was necessary investigate the fisheries occurring in the non-salmon spawning tributaries within YKDNWR waters to better guide management decisions involving these tributaries in the future. Investigating the magnitude of Chinook Salmon harvest in non-salmon spawning tributaries is important to inform discussions at public meetings. This project was aimed to objectively provide facts to managers on the magnitude of use and fishery characteristics in these areas.

For the 2018 Chinook Salmon subsistence fishery season, YDNWR staff collaborated with Bering Sea Fishermen's Association's Community Based Monitoring Program (CBM) to estimate Chinook Salmon subsistence effort and harvest in the prominent non-salmon spawning tributaries (Eenayarak, Tagayarak, Kinak, Kialik, Johnson, and Gweek rivers) of the lower Kuskokwim River. Documenting the effort and harvest of Chinook Salmon in these lower river tributaries is needed for management to: (1) provide additional information on the spatial and temporal distribution of Chinook Salmon harvest in the lower Kuskokwim River; and (2) help guide future management decisions related to the fisheries occurring in these areas. The primary objectives of this study were to: (1) estimate weekly subsistence effort (number of fishing gillnets) in the specified non-salmon spawning tributaries, and (2) estimate weekly subsistence harvest using trip information collected in these non-salmon spawning tributaries.

METHODS

Data Sources

In order to estimate fishing effort and salmon harvest in the non-salmon spawning tributaries, two primary sources of information were needed: (1) gillnet counts from aerial surveys, and (2) trip level information (i.e. harvest, gear, fishing location) collected from the various harvest monitoring projects conducted in the area throughout the duration of the Chinook Salmon subsistence fishery.

Aerial Net Counts

The aerial survey portion of this project followed a stratified two stage sampling design with the time period (May 28 – July 8) stratified by week for a total of six weeks (May 28 - June 3, June 4 - June 10, June 11 - 17, June 18 - June 24, June 25 - July 1, and July 2 - July 8). The primary sampling units for the aerial survey were daily daylight hour flood tides, while the secondary sampling units were flight routes. Daylight hours were chosen in part due to aviation requirements, but also due to the assumption that much of the fishing in the non-salmon tributaries occurred during daylight hours. Flood tides were chosen because of the assumption that subsistence fishers would target milling salmon most actively in non-salmon spawning tributaries during this portion of the tidal cycle. The number of surveys each week were determined by logistical constraints (i.e. pilot availability, budget, etc.). Aerial survey schedules were generated by randomly selecting without replacement four daily daylight hour flood tides from each weekly strata. Each of the four selected daily daylight hour flood tides were then randomly assigned with replacement one of four possible flight routes to ensure tributaries were not counted repeatedly at the same times. The four flight paths were the following:

- 1.) Gweek, Johnson, Kialik, Kinak, Tagarayak, and Eenayarak
- 2.) Johnson, Kialik, Kinak, Tagarayak, Eenayarak, and Gweek
- 3.) Eenayarak, Tagarayak, Kinak, Kialik, Johnson, and Gweek
- 4.) Gweek, Eenayarak, Tagarayak, Kinak, Kialik, and Johnson

The non-salmon spawning tributaries in this study were selected because they are non-mainstem tributaries that receive the most fishing effort located within YDNWR boundaries. The tributaries selected are also mentioned by name in historical Federal special actions and Alaska Department of Fish and Game emergency orders.

When a non-salmon tributary flight was scheduled during a scheduled mainstem block opener (times open to fishing with a gillnet), the non-salmon tributary flight was flown during the mainstem flight that was the most consistent with the sampling unit of the non-salmon tributary schedule (i.e. during a flood tide).

All flights were flown during daylight hours, departing from Bethel no later 0800 for morning flights and no later than 2130 for evening flights. Flights were scheduled to start counts 90 minutes before peak high tide in Bethel during the flood stage of the tidal cycle. In cases where flights could not start 90 minutes before peak high tide due to logistical or personnel issues, flights were either pushed up or down in time, but remained scheduled during the flood tide period selected for the sample. Flights followed the same general path inside the tributaries surveyed. Flights were flown from the confluence of the tributaries with the mainstem Kuskokwim River to around one mile above the confluence. Gillnets were counted on both banks, as well as in the middle of the tributary.

The pilot and observer worked together to record the number of drift gillnets and set gillnets fishing during all aerial surveys, so the survey was considered a complete census; therefore, no observational error was assumed.

Harvest Information

Complete trip interviews were obtained through “creel surveys” conducted by the Orutsararmiut Native Council (ONC) representatives at the Bethel boat harbor and Bethel area fish camps, and by community based monitoring program representatives (Bering Sea Fisherman’s Association; BSFA) located in Akiachak, Akiak, Kwethluk, Napaskiak, and Tuntutuliak. These interviews were conducted to estimate harvest during the directed Chinook Salmon fishing opportunities in the mainstem Kuskokwim River. I was unable to create an independent survey program for the purposes of this study prior to the start of the

season; however, I hoped that this ongoing creel survey would provide the platform to collect harvest information by BSFA surveyors from lower river subsistence users fishing in the non-salmon spawning tributaries. The key pieces of information collected in each interview included:

- The day fishing occurred
- The location of the trip
- The type of net used
- The start and end times of the trip
- The total number of hours the net was fishing
- The length of the net used (in feet)
- The total harvest of Chinook Salmon, Chum Salmon (*Oncorhynchus keta*), Sockeye Salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*), and the various species of whitefish

An additional section denoting the general location of the non-salmon spawning tributaries of interest in this study was added to the maps used by the interviewers to help the interviewee point out the location of the fishing trip to gather trip information from the non-salmon spawning tributaries. Otherwise, this project did not significantly change existing survey methodologies.

Unfortunately, the sample size and distribution of interviews of subsistence harvesters to inform harvest estimates in the non-salmon spawning tributaries was not sufficient to allow unbiased estimates of catch (**Table 1**).

Net Effort Expansion

A simulation approach using parametric bootstrap was used to estimate netting effort (number of gillnets that were fished each week) and the resulting uncertainty across the non-salmon spawning tributaries. Observed net counts were summed across tributaries by gear type (i.e. set and drift gillnets).

Two separate generalized linear models (GLM) were used to estimate mean set and drift gillnet efforts, with sampling period as a fixed effect. Model structure is as specified below:

- 1.) Distribution of Observations: $y_{t,j} \sim NB(\lambda_t, \lambda_t + \frac{\lambda_t^2}{\theta})$
- 2.) Linear Predictor: $\eta_t = \eta + \tau_t$
- 3.) Link Function: $\eta_t = \log(\lambda_t)$

The distribution of the observations (observed set and drift gillnet counts within each week, t) were treated as a negative binomial process, modeled as a continuous mixture of Poisson distributions with gamma distributed means. The negative binomial distribution was chosen because of additional analysis that showed that using the Poisson distribution resulted in the overdispersion parameter much >1 . This part of the analysis was conducted in RStudio 3.4.3 using the function `glm.nb` (MASS library; R Development Core Team, 2008).

After fitting the GLM to estimate the means and theta coefficient, $i = 1000$ datasets were simulated by gear type using the function `rnegbin` in R, which is a function within the MASS library that generates random outcomes from a negative binomial distribution with mean (λ) and variance $(\lambda + \lambda^2/\theta)$, where θ is parameter that captures additional Poisson variance.

Weekly estimates of gillnetting effort means by gear type (S : set gillnets, D : drift gillnets; superscripts) were then calculated for each simulated dataset (i) to produce empirical distributions of weekly mean net effort ($\bar{x}_{t,i}$ or $\bar{y}_{t,i}$). Distributions of weekly mean net effort were then multiplied by the total number of

daylight hour flood tides in each week (T_t) (range: 7-9 periods, median: 8 periods), which resulted in an empirical weekly distribution of the number of gillnets fished by gear type that would be expected during all daylight hour flood tides each week, $\hat{E}_{t,i}$. This equation is similar to Equation 3 found in Bernard et al. (1998). A simulation based approach was adopted to ensure confidence interval estimates given the domain of gillnet counts is bounded by 0. Once the empirical distribution of expanded gillnetting effort by gear type and sample period were produced, estimates were summarized by taking the mean across all bootstrapped datasets (n), as well as percentile confidence intervals (95%).

$$\hat{E}_{t,i}^S = T_t \bar{x}_{t,i} = T_t * \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j=1}^r x_{t,i,j}, \text{ where } x_{t,i} \sim NB(\lambda_t^S, \lambda_t^S + \frac{\lambda_t^{2S}}{\theta^S})$$

$$\hat{E}_{t,i}^D = T_t \bar{y}_{t,i} = T_t * \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j=1}^r y_{t,i,j}, \text{ where } y_{t,i} \sim NB(\lambda_t^D, \lambda_t^D + \frac{\lambda_t^{2D}}{\theta^D})$$

RESULTS

Effort

Aerial Surveys

At total of 24 aerial flights were scheduled to be flown between 5/28 and 7/5 (4 flights x 6 weeks); however, due to staffing issues, weather, and other logistical issues, only 21 flights were flown (**Table 2** and **3**). Three flights were flown in sampling periods two, four, and six. Six of the flown flights (5/30, 6/6, 6/12, 6/16, 6/29, 7/5) coincided with aerial surveys that were operated to enumerate subsistence effort during netting opportunities in the main-stem of the Kuskokwim River.

Estimated Netting Effort

An estimated a total of 786 gillnets (95% CI: 641 – 931) were fished during all daylight flood tides across all non-salmon tributaries for the six week study period from May 28 – July 8, 2018 (**Table 4; Figure 2**). The estimated total number of gillnets during the first sampling period (May 28 – June 3) was minimal (14 gillnets, 95% CI: 4 – 26); however, the estimated number of gillnets generally increased throughout the month of June, peaking in the fourth sampling period (June 18 – June 24) at an estimated 248 gillnets (95% CI: 159 – 348) (**Table 4; Figure 3**). Following the peak, the estimated number of gillnets decreased over the last two weeks to 96 (95% CI: 54 – 147) (**Table 4; Figure 3**).

The estimates of gillnets fished in the non-salmon tributaries during the length of study was dominated by set nets rather than drift gillnets, although both did show distinct temporal trends (**Table 4; Figures 2** and **4**). An estimated total of 539 set gillnets (95% CI: 426 – 665) were fished during this study, while an estimated 246 (95% CI: 167 – 342) drift gillnets were fished (**Table 4; Figure 2**).

Similar to the previously described pattern for total gillnets, the number of set gillnets fished generally increased from the first sampling period, peaking during the fourth sampling period at an estimated 152 set gillnets (95% CI: 90 – 231). However, it should be noted that the estimated number of set gillnets fished after the second sampling period remained relatively constant with only a slight decline after the peak (**Table 4; Figure 4**).

The estimated number of drift gillnets fished showed a very distinctive pattern compared to the estimated number of set gillnets fished. The estimated number of drift gillnets fished exhibited a gradual linear

increase during the first half of June, which was followed by a substantial increase during the latter half of June (**Table 4; Figure 4**). Following this peak, the estimated number of drift gillnets fished considerably decreased to similar numbers estimated during first sampling period (**Table 4; Figure 4**).

Observed Tributary Trends and Composition in Netting Effort

For the purposes of this analysis, gillnetting effort estimates were not produced at the tributary level because of low sample sizes. Instead, estimates of effort were produced across all sampled non-salmon tributaries. However, this does not mean that important subsistence fishery patterns and general usage in the non-salmon tributaries cannot be discerned from the observed tributary counts. The results in this section are counts rather than estimates of numbers of gillnets fished due to the low sample sizes and will highlight observed trends.

Overall, the Johnson and Gweek rivers were the most utilized non-salmon tributaries during the study (**Table 5; Figure 5**). Combined, these tributaries accounted for approximately 70% of all the gillnets observed during the study period. Each of these tributaries exhibited a steady increase in the average number of gillnets counted each week, with both rivers peaking in the fourth sampling period (9 – 13 gillnets/flight) (**Table 6; Figure 6**). The average number of gillnets in the Johnson River dropped significantly after the fourth sampling period, while the Gweek River slightly decreased and plateaued following the fourth sampling period (**Table 6; Figure 6**). In terms of gear types utilized, the Johnson River exhibited substantially more drift gillnetting effort than the Gweek River, especially during the fourth and fifth sampling period (**Table 6; Figure 6**). Both rivers displayed similar trends in set gillnet usage; however, the average number of set gillnets in the Gweek River were consistently two to three times the amount of set gillnets as compared to the Johnson River (**Table 6; Figure 6**).

Of the remaining tributaries, the Kinak and Tagarayak accounted for approximately 20% of all gillnets observed (**Table 5; Figure 5**). The Kinak River exhibited a bi-modal pattern in average number of gillnets counted, peaking in the third sampling period at approximately 4 gillnets per flight, decreasing during the fourth sampling period (~ 1 gillnet per flight), then increasing again 4 gillnets per flight in the fifth sampling period (**Table 6; Figure 6**). The Tagarayak River displayed a very consistent pattern in average number of gillnets counted between sampling periods two and four (2 – 4 gillnets per flight), before dropping off significantly in sampling periods five and six (0 – 0.5 gillnets per flight) (**Table 6; Figure 6**). Only set gillnets were observed in the Tagarayak River. The Kinak River exhibited a very distinct gear type utilization transition with more set gillnets observed during the first half of the study in comparison to drift gillnets, while during the latter half of the study, more drift gillnets were observed in comparison to set gillnets.

The Eenayarak and Kialik rivers accounted for the remaining 10% of all gillnets observed (**Table 5; Figure 5**). Average gillnet counts in the Eenayarak River steadily increased throughout the length of the study, peaking in the fourth sampling period (1 gillnet per flight) before steadily decreasing to 0 gillnets per flight during the latter half of the study (**Table 6; Figure 6**). The Kialik River displayed a variable, yet consistent increase in the average number of gillnets observed during the length of the study. Peaks average counts were between 1 – 2 gillnets per flight and occurred in the third and fifth sampling period. For both tributaries, the primary gear method utilized was drift gillnetting, especially in the Kialik River (**Table 6; Figure 6**).

Survey Interviews

A total of 18 interviews were collected on trips occurring in the non-salmon spawning tributaries (**Tables 7, 8, and 9**). Almost all respondents reported using gillnets between 4 inches and 6 inches mesh size ($n = 16$) (**Table 8**). The two reported gillnets over 6 inches mesh size were drift gillnets and were used in the

Kialik River (7 inches and 7 ½ inches mesh size) (**Table 8**). Set gillnets mesh size ranged from 4 inches to 6 inches, with the most common mesh size being 5 7/8 inches, while drift gillnets mesh size ranged from 5 3/8 inches to 7 ½ inches with the most common mesh size being 5 ½ inches (**Table 9**). Gillnet lengths for drift gillnets ranged from 150 – 300 feet with the most common length being 300 feet, while set gillnets lengths ranged from 40 – 300 feet with the most common length being 300 feet (**Table 9**). Drift gillnet soak times ranged from 30 minutes to 3 hours, while set gillnets soaked between 30 minutes and 20 hours (**Table 9**).

DISCUSSION

The objectives of this study were partially achieved. While the project estimated fishing effort in the non-salmon spawning tributaries, the project could not reliably estimate harvest. However, the study was not insignificant and I feel the biggest contributions are: (1) eliciting general patterns and trends in gear utilization and timing within and among tributaries; (2) providing a measure for the magnitude of fishing effort within the non-salmon spawning tributaries and how the magnitude of fishing effort changes over the course of the subsistence fishery; and (3) providing a comparison of fishing effort in the non-salmon spawning tributaries versus the fishing effort in the mainstem Kuskokwim River during salmon directed opportunities. These contributions improve our understanding of subsistence fishing in the non-salmon spawning tributaries and will better inform future management.

Through this study, I identified general trends and patterns in gear, fishery timing, and the magnitude of fishing effort within the non-salmon spawning tributaries within YDNWR waters. Total effort was low in late May, gradually increased to a peak toward the end of June, and then decreased into early July. This is relatively consistent with the magnitude of Chinook Salmon migrating into the Kuskokwim River over the course of the summer. In terms of overall gear types employed, set nets were overwhelmingly utilized more than drift nets in the non-salmon spawning tributaries; however, specific temporal patterns were recognizable. Set nets were utilized earlier in the season before plateauing, while the utilization of drift nets gradually increased during month of June before substantially dropping during the first week in July. These patterns in the utilization of drift nets matched with current knowledge about the characteristics of the subsistence fishery, where subsistence users put in more fishing effort when fish abundance is high. In this manner, subsistence users maximize their efficiency and minimize wasted resources such as gas and time.

From this study, I was able to rank tributaries based on gear use and magnitude of fishing effort. The Johnson and Gweek rivers received the highest fishing effort, accounting for 70% of all the gillnets counted in the aerial surveys. This observation makes sense as these tributaries are closer to the population centers within the drainage. The Johnson River appeared to be mixed use in terms of gear type employed, with set gillnets increasing throughout the season before plateauing at a certain level, while drift gillnet utilization was initially small, but substantially increasing during the latter half of June. The Gweek River appeared to be a very popular set gillnet location with only a small number of consistently counted drift gillnets observed during much of the study.

While the study tributaries below the Johnson River did not show nearly the amount of fishing effort observed in the Johnson or Gweek rivers, it is important to note that the two tributaries closest to Tuntutuliak (Kinak and Tagarayak rivers) were observed to be the most utilized rivers below the Johnson. The Tagarayak River appears to be a popular set gillnet location as only set nets were counted during this study. The Kinak River is mixed use that displays a switch in gear methodology (i.e. set gillnets more utilized in the early part of June before giving way to drift gillnets during the latter part of June). The remaining two rivers: the Eenayarak River and Kialik River, appear to primarily be drift gillnet locations.

As some aerial surveys monitoring fishing effort in the non-salmon spawning tributaries coincided with

aerial surveys conducted in the mainstem Kuskokwim River (*see* Staton 2018), I was able to compare effort in both locations (**Table 10**). Six aerial surveys in the non-salmon spawning tributaries coincided with aerial surveys conducted in the mainstem Kuskokwim River during set and drift gillnet opportunities (5/30, 6/6, 6/12, 6/16, 6/29, and 7/5). Combining data from all six non-salmon tributary surveys, the number of gillnets observed in the non-salmon spawning was less than the maximum number of gillnets observed in the mainstem Kuskokwim River. Across these six surveys, the total number of set gillnets observed in the non-salmon spawning tributaries was roughly one-third of the number of set gillnets observed in the mainstem Kuskokwim River (50 vs. 158 set nets). The total number of drift gillnets observed in the non-salmon spawning tributaries was approximately 2% of the maximum number of drift gillnets observed in the mainstem Kuskokwim River (29 vs. 1,068 drift gillnets). To put the magnitude of drift gillnet utilization in the non-salmon spawning tributaries into perspective, the total number of drift gillnets estimated in the non-salmon spawning tributaries from 5/28 – 7/8 was 246 (95% CI: 167 – 342), while the maximum observed number of drift gillnets in each of the mainstem Kuskokwim River drift gillnets opportunities during that same time period ranged from 101 – 331 drift gillnets, with a total of 1,387 observed drift gillnets over the course of the seven mainstem opportunities. Drift gillnetting in the non-salmon spawning tributaries over the course of this six-week sampling period appears to be approximately equivalent to the maximum number of drift gillnets that would be observed during a single 12-hour mainstem Kuskokwim River salmon directed opportunity.

Although I feel the aerial component of this survey did a good job to characterize fishing effort within the non-salmon tributaries, there were issues that may have biased our characterization. Surveys only occurred during daylight hour flood tides. Daylight hours were assumed *a-priori* as the time period in which most effort occurred in the non-salmon spawning tributaries, and the survey also assumed that subsistence fishers would target milling salmon most actively in non-salmon spawning tributaries during the flood portion of the tidal cycle. From the onset of the survey, I observed gillnets in most of the tributaries during the flood tide cycle. However, in conversations with some subsistence users who fish the area indicated some fishing effort occurs when the tide switches from flood tide to ebb tide. If this new knowledge is true, then our survey did not sample a full representation of the fishery occurring in the studied non-salmon spawning tributaries. For a future survey, this could be easily remedied by including daylight hour ebb tides into the sampling pool, then sample using probability proportion to size methods to weight the creation of the final sampling schedule. If this were done, effort estimates would be expanded to include all daylight hour tides.

Another potential issue was with the timing of the flights over the large survey area. In general, the flights were attempted 1.5 hours before high tide in Bethel; however, for most of the tributaries below the Johnson, the tidal delay is 2+ hours. Depending on when the flight was started, this means some of the lower tributaries below the Johnson may have been sampled during the ebb tide, while the tributaries nearer to Bethel were sampled during the flood tide. The solution to this issue is complicated, but future investigations would have to specify the optimum time period that would ensure a high probability of sampling tributaries below and above the Johnson River during each tidal cycle.

This study was unable to meet our second stated objective: to produce a reliable estimate of harvest within the non-salmon spawning tributaries. This inability to produce a reliable harvest estimate was primarily because of the minimal number of interviews collected from fishing in these locations. Only 18 of the 1,020 interviews contained trip level information for the non-salmon spawning tributaries of interest. Additionally, because of the small sample size, temporal and spatial coverage of the interviews were inadequate. Trip level information were only collected during the six Chinook Salmon directed subsistence harvest opportunities. No interview data were available when the mainstem of the Kuskokwim River was closed. Almost all interviews from the non-salmon spawning tributaries were collected during the June 16 ($n = 6$) and June 24 ($n = 9$) survey dates. Spatially, at least one interview was obtained from the Eenayarak, Kinak, Kialik, and Gweek rivers, while no interview information was collected from the Tagararak or Johnson rivers. A majority of the interviews ($n = 10$) were collected in the Kialik River. There are

numerous factors which likely limited interview information from the non-salmon spawning tributaries. For example, most of the interviews were conducted in association with periods when the lower Kuskokwim mainstem was open to subsistence fishing, so harvesters were more likely to fish in the mainstem where salmon densities were higher. Second, there is a general reluctance for subsistence harvesters to discuss harvest results, an aspect likely exacerbated if harvesting salmon in a tributary nominally deemed to be a non-salmon spawning tributary.

Although reliable estimates of harvest could not be obtained through the 18 interviews collected from subsistence users fishing in the non-salmon spawning tributaries, I did attempt to produce a salmon harvest estimate using catch per trip estimates by gear type as calculated during the block openers in the mainstem Kuskokwim River for 2018 (Staton 2018). Essentially, bootstrapped mainstem Kuskokwim River catch estimates were summed by appropriate strata, divided by the estimated number of trips by gear type to produce a catch per trip estimate, and then multiplied by the estimated effort by gear type from our study. This process produced empirical harvest distributions for each salmon species by sampling period and gear type. This calculation makes an untested assumption that subsistence user success rates are the same as the mainstem Kuskokwim River and that the composition of fish available for harvest is similar to that of the mainstem Kuskokwim River. I additionally assume that similar gear types, net lengths, and mesh sizes are utilized in both the tributaries and the mainstem. From the small amount of interview data that was collected in the non-salmon tributaries, the second assumption seems to be met. Furthermore, the following harvest estimates are highly uncertain and should not be used for management purposes.

Based on these assumptions and the methodology briefly described above, the estimated total number of Chinook Salmon harvested during the study period, between May 28 – July 8, 2018, ranged from 5,000 to 8,000 fish. Additionally, the estimated total number of Chum Salmon harvested during the same period ranged from 7,000 to 16,000 fish, while the estimate total number of Sockeye Salmon harvested ranged from 9,000 to 17,000 fish. Under these conditions, many of the Chinook Salmon were harvested between June 11 and June 24. To put the Chinook Salmon harvest into perspective, single day mainstem harvest of Chinook Salmon during this same time period during each of the 12 hour opportunities on June 12, 16, and 24 ranged between 5,000 and 6,000 fish. It is incredibly important to restate that these harvest estimates are highly likely to be biased because of the assumptions stated in the previous paragraph. Although these ranges seem relatively precise, many of the core assumptions were likely violated. The composition of fish available for harvest within these tributaries likely differ from that of the mainstem Kuskokwim River. Certain salmon species like Chum and Sockeye salmon are more bank oriented than Chinook Salmon making them more susceptible to be influenced by the tidal flow into and out of these tributaries, which means that Chum and Sockeye salmon are likely more prevalent in these tributaries than Chinook Salmon. As such, the Chinook Salmon harvest is likely biased high, while Chum and Sockeye salmon harvest numbers may be biased low.

In closing, this was the first attempt to characterize the subsistence fisheries occurring within the non-salmon spawning tributaries. This survey was intended to help inform discussions pertaining to fisheries management occurring in these areas since some stakeholders have identified that fishing levels have increased in the non-salmon spawning tributaries as a result of gillnet restrictions in the mainstem Kuskokwim River. This survey was able to enumerate gillnet effort in these tributaries over a six-week period encompassing the majority of the Chinook Salmon subsistence fishery. From these aerial surveys, I was able to elicit general patterns and trends in gear utilization and timing, but unable to enumerate harvest in these tributaries.

If future studies to estimate effort and harvest in the non-salmon spawning tributaries are considered, I make the following recommendations:

- 1.) Redesign the aerial surveys to minimize potential sources of bias associated with non-

- representative timing,
- 2.) Restructure sampling effort roughly proportion to fishing effort, such that the non-salmon spawning tributaries that received the most fishing effort (i.e. Gweek and Johnson rivers) are sampled most intensively, and most importantly,
 - 3.) Ensure a sampling program is available that can provide representative fisher performance (i.e. harvest and effort) data sufficient to generate Chinook Salmon harvest estimates with minimal bias.

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LITERATURE CITED

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Table and Figures

Figure 1: Map of lower Kuskokwim River. Sampled non-salmon spawning tributaries are dark blue, with exception to Akulikutak River and Columbia Creek

Table 1: Trip interviews by tributary for each opportunity

Tributary	Opportunities						Total
	5/30	6/6	6/16	6/24	6/29	7/5	
Eenayarak River	0	0	4	0	0	0	4
Tagarayak River	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kinak River	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
Kialik River	0	1	1	8	0	0	10
Johnson River	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gweek River	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Total	0	1	6	9	0	2	18

Table 2: Raw drift gillnet counts from each flight by tributary.

Week	Date	Tributaries: Drift Net Counts						Total
		Eenayarak	Tagarayak	Kinak	Kialik	Johnson	Gweek	
1	05/28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	05/30	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	06/02	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	06/03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	06/06	1	0	0	0	1	0	2
	06/07	1	0	0	0	1	0	2
	06/10	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
3	06/11	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	06/12	2	0	1	2	1	1	7
	06/15	0	0	0	4	1	1	6
	06/16	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
4	06/19	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
	06/21	3	0	0	1	14	2	20
	06/22	0	0	2	0	7	2	11
5	06/26	0	0	4	1	12	1	18
	06/28	0	0	4	0	11	2	17
	06/29	1	0	4	3	7	0	15
	07/01	0	0	0	0	1	2	3
6	07/02	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
	07/03	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	07/05	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Total	5/28 - 7/5	9	0	16	12	61	14	112

Table 3: Raw set gillnet counts from each flight by tributary.

Week	Date	Tributaries: Set Net Counts						Total
		Eenayarak	Tagarayak	Kinak	Kialik	Johnson	Gweek	
1	05/28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	05/30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	06/02	0	1	0	1	0	1	3
	06/03	0	1	0	0	1	0	2
2	06/06	0	3	2	0	1	8	14
	06/07	0	2	1	0	3	3	9
	06/10	0	5	3	0	6	6	20
3	06/11	0	4	3	0	5	6	18
	06/12	0	4	5	0	6	6	21
	06/15	1	4	5	0	1	5	16
	06/16	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
4	06/19	0	4	0	0	3	5	12
	06/21	0	3	1	0	9	10	23
	06/22	0	1	0	0	6	9	16
5	06/26	0	2	0	0	2	5	9
	06/28	1	0	4	3	3	7	18
	06/29	0	0	0	0	2	7	9
	07/01	0	0	0	0	2	5	7
6	07/02	0	0	0	0	7	8	15
	07/03	0	0	0	0	3	7	10
	07/05	0	0	0	0	0	4	4
Total	5/28 - 7/5	2	34	25	4	60	103	228

Table 4: Estimated number of gillnets during each sampling period.

Method	Week	Date	Mean	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
All Nets	1	05/28 - 06/03	14	4	26
	2	06/04 - 06/10	130	80	192
	3	06/11 - 06/17	129	88	177
	4	06/18 - 06/24	248	159	348
	5	06/25 - 07/01	169	110	238
	6	07/01 - 07/08	96	54	147
All Nets	Total	05/28 - 07/08	786	641	931
Drift	1	05/28 - 06/03	4	0	10
	2	06/04 - 06/10	16	3	32
	3	06/11 - 06/17	28	10	52
	4	06/18 - 06/24	95	39	174
	5	06/25 - 07/01	94	46	154
	6	07/01 - 07/08	9	0	21
Drift	Total	05/28 - 07/08	246	167	342
Set	1	05/28 - 06/03	10	2	20
	2	06/04 - 06/10	114	67	176
	3	06/11 - 06/17	101	63	145
	4	06/18 - 06/24	152	90	231
	5	06/25 - 07/01	75	44	110
	6	07/01 - 07/08	87	45	135
Set	Total	05/28 - 07/08	539	426	665

Table 5: Total number of gillnets observed at each tributary during the study.

Tributary	Drift Net	Set Net	All Nets
Eenayarak	9	2	11
Tagarayak	0	34	34
Kinak	16	25	41
Kialik	12	4	16
Johnson	61	60	121
Gweek	14	103	117
Total	112	228	340

Figure 2: Estimated number of nets by gear type.

Figure 3: Estimated total number of nets by sampling period.

Figure 4: Estimated number of nets by gear type each sampling period.

Figure 5: Observed net counts by gear type and tributary.

Table 6: Average number of nets observed in each sampling period by tributary.

Method	Week	Tributaries: Avg. Net Counts Per Flight					
		Eenayarak	Tagarayak	Kinak	Kialik	Johnson	Gweek
Drift	1	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.33	0.00
	3	0.50	0.00	0.25	1.50	1.00	0.75
	4	1.00	0.00	0.67	0.33	7.33	1.33
	5	0.25	0.00	3.00	1.00	7.75	1.25
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.00	0.67
Set	1	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.25	0.25	0.25
	2	0.00	3.33	2.00	0.00	3.33	5.67
	3	0.25	3.00	3.50	0.00	3.00	4.50
	4	0.00	2.67	0.33	0.00	6.00	8.00
	5	0.25	0.50	1.00	0.75	2.25	6.00
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.33	6.33
Total	1	0.25	0.50	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
	2	0.67	3.33	2.00	0.00	4.67	5.67
	3	0.75	3.00	3.75	1.50	4.00	5.25
	4	1.00	2.67	1.00	0.33	13.33	9.33
	5	0.50	0.50	4.00	1.75	10.00	7.25
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	3.33	7.00

Table 7: Trip interviews by tributary for each gear type

Tributary	Drift Net	Set Net	All Nets
Eenayarak River	0	4	4
Tagarayak River	0	0	0
Kinak River	0	2	2
Kialik River	9	1	10
Johnson River	0	0	0
Gweek River	0	2	2
Total	9	9	18

Table 8: Gillnet characteristics by gear type and tributary

Tributary	Drift Net		Set Net		All Nets	
	<=6"	>6"	<=6"	>6"	<=6"	>6"
Eenayarak River	0	0	4	0	4	0
Tagarayak River	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kinak River	0	0	2	0	2	0
Kialik River	7	2	1	0	8	2
Johnson River	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gweek River	2	0	0	0	2	0
Total	9	2	7	0	16	2

Figure 6: Average total gillnet count by sampling period in each tributary

Table 9: Net characteristics by method

Method	Range & Mode		Range & Mode		Soak Time Range (hrs)
	Mesh Size	Mesh Size	Net Length	Net Length	
Drift	5 3/8 - 7 1/2 "	5 1/2 "	150 - 300'	300'	0.5 - 3
Set	4 - 6 "	5 7/8 "	40 - 300'	300'	0.5 - 20
Total	4 - 7 1/2 "	5 1/2 "	40 - 300'	300'	0.5 - 20

Table 10: Comparison of net counts during aerial surveys in non-salmon spawning tributaries and mainstem Kuskokwim River

	Date	Set Nets		Drift Nets	
		Tributary	Mainstem	Tributary	Mainstem
Mainstem Open	5/30	0	11	2	0
	6/6	14	70	2	0
	6/12	21	31	7	331
	6/16	2	20	2	319
	6/24	NA	18	NA	319
	6/29	9	13	15	317
	7/5	4	13	1	101
Mainstem Open	Total	50	176	29	1387
Mainstem Closed	5/28	0	NA	0	NA
	6/2	3	NA	1	NA
	6/3	2	NA	0	NA
	6/7	9	NA	2	NA
	6/10	20	NA	2	NA
	6/11	18	NA	1	NA
	6/15	16	NA	6	NA
	6/19	12	NA	1	NA
	6/21	23	NA	20	NA
	6/22	16	NA	11	NA
	6/26	9	NA	18	NA
	6/28	18	NA	17	NA
	7/1	7	NA	3	NA
	7/2	15	NA	1	NA
7/3	10	NA	1	NA	
Mainstem Closed	Total	178	NA	84	NA
Overall	Grand Total	228	176	113	1387